

MANIFESTATION OF THE MULTIDIMENSIONALITY OF THE CONCEPT FEAR IN ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS-EMOTIVES

Bekmuratova Aydana

Uzbekistan state world languages university

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Annotation: Information regarding the idea of its structure and function in linguistics is provided in this article. This page is helpful because it clarifies the ambiguity and complexity of the idea of dread in English phraseological units emotives. In addition to word definitions from dictionaries, concepts are also developed in the human mind based on individual and societal cultural-historical experiences; the more comprehensive these experiences, the more expansive the bounds of concepts.

Key words: Linguistics, concept, fear, phraseological unit, method, world picture, emotion, universal, cognition, formation.

Every language has its own development laws, which are determined by the qualities and intrinsic capacities of the language. English phraseological unit construction contains unique features as well. It is well known that as a phraseology forms, a word combination obtains every element that makes up a phraseological structure.

The subject of how phraseological units (PhU) are generated has garnered increasing attention from phraseologists in recent years. This is because one of the least researched topics in linguistics continues to be the content of language units, particularly the structural-semantic aspects of PhUs. To understand the relationship between the semantic-phraseological variants of PhU, it is crucial to generalize the primary phraseoderivation techniques.

The language of human emotions is included in the concept of FEAR. The lexeme characteristic of the English idea of dread, according to the study's historical-etymological research, corresponds to the Latin words timor, pavor, and metus. Tim is a root that is frequently found in Romance languages; in English, it is called mor. Tim takes part in the word fear (sincere from the fear) as a root, which gives rise to the words timor, pavor, and metus. This word came into use in English in the fourteenth century, coming from the later Latin word cordialis, which means "sincere."

The word "fear" has two distinct meanings in the English language, according to its original dictionary definition: 1) an uncomfortable feeling brought on by the possibility of danger 2) Anguish or injury. Fear is a term used to describe fright in English. The following concepts are prevalent in the semantics of fear

lexemes: The word "fear" conjures up images of a sensation that stirs up emotions and pumps blood.

The fear lexeme also has meanings close to emotions in concepts such as enemy, hate, and unhappiness.. For instance, freeze the blood, remain vigilant, give the victim the creeps, cause the victim's flesh to tremble, cry before the victim is injured, make the victim's hair stand on end, put the victim's heart in their mouth, or resemble a death head on a mopstick. The term "fear" refers to phraseological elements that describe an individual's tense emotional state, as though they are anticipating something bad happening to them.

It is crucial that dread manifests itself in a variety of ways, both in terms of timing and intensity. Psychologists have made numerous statements regarding this. "A person may experience fear as a transient or ongoing emotion brought on by actual or perceived threat. Fear is a mental condition that manifests as distressing and agonizing events, panic attacks, and self-preservation behaviors. Phrasological units are used to describe the concept of fear: receive a shock, take alarm, be terrified of one's shadow, go down in one's boots, once bit, twice shy, as scared as a rabbit, confuse smb, halt to look at a fence, and so on (a total of 8). The following is a representation of definitional analysis: become afraid of one's shadow → to have a sudden fear when you walking down → to become anxious → dreadful condition → timorousness → genuine grounds of fear → emotional state; occasionally you become scared → shock of a sudden, startling, and typically short → lived fear → dread → weakness or cowardice → emotional state.

The conceptual group of phraseological units with the integral feature "fear" is intriguing overall because it lets you define various emotional states with varying degrees of unexpectedness, unconditionality, strength, turbulence, duration of manifestation, and dependence on real or imagined negative factors. The semantic originality of phraseological units reflecting the concept of fear is due to the combination of the archiseme "emotional state", the integral seme "fear", and the differential semes "scare", "fright", "horror", "dread".

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